

APPROVED

By Order No. V- 291 of 25 April 2025

Commander of the General Jonas Žemaitis Military Academy of Lithuania

**ACTION PLAN FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF COMMITMENTS UNDER THE
AGREEMENT ON THE REFORM OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH ASSESSMENT
GENERAL JONAS ŽEMAITIS MILITARY ACADEMY OF LITHUANIA**

General Jonas Žemaitis Military Academy of Lithuania (hereinafter referred to as MAL) is the only higher military education institution in Lithuania, continuing the traditions of the Military School named after the First President of Lithuania, established on January 25, 1919. The mission of MAL is to become a unique national university where academic studies and military training are harmoniously integrated, ensuring the comprehensive education and development of responsible officer leaders, conducting high-quality scientific research, and promoting the principles of lifelong learning to ensure a highly qualified officer corps for the Lithuanian Armed Forces. The vision of MAL is to become an internationally recognized university and competence center for the training of officer leaders in the fields of national security, defence, and military studies, offering relevant and competitive academic programs, conducting high-level research, and fostering an effective network of cooperation with social and academic partners.

MAL academic staff is divided into five research groups:

- Governance of Security Institutions
- Defence Economics and Management
- Management of Logistics and Defence Technologies
- World Politics
- Security Policy

The priority research areas at MAL are Political Science and Management, which form the basis of the scientific research conducted.

MAL seeks to enable researchers to carry out advanced, internationally recognized research aligned with its fields of study, thus ensuring the integration and synergy of academic studies and research.

In September 2024, MAL joined the CoARA (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment) coalition, expressing its commitment to implementing the reform of research assessment.

In line with the principles set out in the coalition agreement of August 9, 2024, MAL committed to developing an action plan under which the institution's documents related to research assessment will be reviewed and updated in accordance with the core principles of CoARA.

In order to implement the amendments to the Law on Science and Studies of the Republic of Lithuania and other related legal acts, which define the mandatory and recommended competencies and the scope of abilities corresponding to each career stage of lecturers and research and artistic staff, the Regulations on the Recruitment, Performance Evaluation and Certification of Lecturers and Research and Artistic Staff at the General Jonas Žemaitis Military Academy of Lithuania were prepared in 2024 and updated by Order No. V-47 of the Commander of the General Jonas Žemaitis Military Academy of Lithuania on 27 January 2025.

The table below presents the MAL Action Plan for the Implementation of the Research Assessment Reform Commitments. The plan is intended to be reviewed and updated annually to reflect the ongoing collaboration between working groups and the academic community, including researchers across all levels and disciplines, as well as heads of research activities.

CoARA principle ¹	Description of the principle ²	Planned MAL activities	Planned result	2025		2026		2027		2028	
1. Recognize the diversity of contributions to research and research careers, considering the needs and nature of research.	<p>The aim of this commitment is to help expand the recognition of diversity in research practices, activities, and careers, taking into account the specific nature of research disciplines and other research activities. The commitment aims for changes in evaluation practices to enable the recognition of a wide diversity: significant contributions of researchers to science and societal well-being, including various outcomes not limited to journal publications; integrating practices into activities that help ensure the reliability, openness, transparency, and inclusivity of research and the research process, including peer review, teamwork, and collaboration, as well as</p>	<p>1.1. Establish a working group representing the main scientific fields of the MAL to determine the evaluation criteria for the competencies of career stages of researchers (lecturers and research staff) and propose possible changes according to CoARA principles, policies, and guidelines.</p>	<p>1.1. A working group has been established and proposals have been made on how to update the evaluation criteria for the competencies of career stages of researchers (lecturers and research staff) as needed.</p>		X		X	X			

¹ CoARA principles <https://cora.eu/agreement/the-commitments/>

² Description of the CoARA principle, translated according to the description of principles provided on the CoARA website (<https://coara.eu/agreement/the-commitments/>)

	activities involving teaching, leadership, supervision, training, and mentoring.	1.2. Prepare guidelines for research supporting studies for the 2026–2029 plans , considering the recognition of diversity in research practices, activities, and careers .	1.2. Guidelines for research supporting studies for the 2026–2029 plans have been prepared, considering recognition of the diversity in research practices, activities, and careers of scientists (lecturers and researchers).				X		X		X
2. Base the evaluation of scientific research primarily on qualitative assessment, with peer review as the main criterion and responsible use of quantitative indicators.	The aim of this commitment is to facilitate the transition to research evaluation criteria that focus on quality, while recognizing that responsible use of quantitative indicators can aid in evaluation if meaningful and appropriate, which depends on the context. The commitment aims to ensure that peer review processes are developed to meet the core principles of	2.1. Establish and implement qualitative research evaluation principles that prioritize peer review and responsible use of quantitative indicators, adhering to the principles of expert assessment, transparency, and ethics.	2.1. Established qualitative research evaluation principles are based on peer review and responsible use of quantitative indicators, adhering to the principles of transparency, ethics, and gender equality.				X	X			
		2.2. Organize workshops for evaluators to ensure they apply a responsible approach to quantitative	2.2. The newly acquired knowledge of evaluators will enable the application of					X		X	

<p>evaluating individual researchers).</p>	<p>research organizations independently form evaluation practices instead of following criteria and methodologies set by external commercial companies. Metrics do not always reflect the quality of research results, their significance, and their impact on society.</p>	<p>activity results, strengthening partnerships with organizations that have significant scientific expertise in specific scientific interest directions, rather than focusing on research organization rankings.</p>	<p>collaboration with organizations that have accumulated significant experience in the respective fields.</p>							
<p>4. Allocate resources for the reform of research evaluation necessary for the organizational changes committed to being implemented.</p>	<p>The purpose of this commitment is to ensure that organizations allocate the necessary resources (budget or staff capacity) to improve research evaluation practices within the agreed timeframe. This commitment aims to ensure that each organization allocates as many resources as needed to implement changes that allow adherence to principles and fulfillment of commitments.</p>	<p>4.1. Plan the budget for 2026–2028, dedicated to carrying out the reform of research evaluation, including both administrative and academic staff.</p>	<p>4.1. The planned budget for 2026–2028, necessary to implement the reform of research evaluation and to include both administrative and academic staff as needed.</p>			X		X		X
<p>5. Review and develop research evaluation criteria, tools, and processes.</p>	<p>Criteria set for departments and institutions. By directly involving researchers at all stages of their careers, review and develop the evaluation criteria for research departments and organizations conducting</p>	<p>5.1. Review and update the evaluation criteria for research departments, considering CoARA principles.</p>	<p>5.1. Updated evaluation criteria, considering the specifics of research activities of different departments, ensuring responsible use of metrics and interoperability.</p>	X		X	X			

	<p>scientific research, while promoting interoperability. This commitment will ensure that national, regional, and organizational institutions and evaluation agencies review and, if necessary, develop the evaluation criteria for departments and organizations conducting research activities according to principles. This will promote the responsible use of metrics in evaluating research departments and organizations and help avoid contradictions or inconsistencies between research evaluation, researchers, and research-performing organizations. It will also ensure the interoperability of adapted or newly created evaluation processes. Criteria set for projects and scientists. By directly involving researchers at all career stages in preparing to review and develop evaluation criteria, tools, and processes for research projects, research groups, and their members, adapted</p>	<p>5.2. Conduct consultations with research groups and project leaders to identify existing evaluation shortcomings and improve the evaluation criteria and processes for research projects and groups.</p>	<p>5.2. Improved and adapted evaluation criteria and processes that reflect the diversity of activities of research groups and projects, ensuring the importance of context in evaluating scientific projects.</p>						X		X
--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	---	--	---

	<p>to their application context. This commitment will allow for the recognition of diverse research activities and practices by reviewing and improving evaluation criteria, tools, and processes. It will ensure that organizations review their processes and make tangible changes by creating existing or new evaluation methods individually or in collaboration with others, following principles.</p>									
<p>6. Increase awareness of research evaluation reform and ensure transparent information, guidance, and training about evaluation criteria and processes and their application.</p>	<p>The aim of this commitment is to ensure that organizations provide all participants with sufficient knowledge about the reform. This commitment aims to ensure that organizations transparently inform about the criteria, tools, and processes applied in the evaluation of scientific research and train researchers and evaluators to use them. Organizations should inform about the evaluation processes and the tools and criteria used, publicly publish guidelines for evaluation methods, and</p>	<p>6.1. Publicly publish guidelines for the criteria, tools, and processes of scientific research evaluation, intended for both researchers and evaluators, ensuring transparency and dissemination of knowledge about the goals of the reform.</p>	<p>6.1. Publicly accessible guidelines for scientific research evaluation, which transparently define the evaluation criteria, processes, and tools used.</p>				X			

	train participants in the evaluation process. They should allow evaluated individuals to familiarize themselves with the criteria, data, and deliberation results used in the evaluation, while adhering to confidentiality requirements.										
7. Exchange practices and experiences to facilitate mutual learning both within the Coalition and beyond.	The goal of this commitment is to ensure that organizations exchange information and use it for mutual learning. By exchanging insights, practices, and strategies with institutions implementing CoARA commitments, both nationally and within the Coalition, they can learn from each other, creating a unified system and overcoming emerging challenges. This commitment will ensure that organizations exchange information and use it for mutual learning. It will help avoid fragmentation and allow more advanced participants to share methods and experiences.	7.1. Organize periodic experience exchange visits/events with other national and international research institutions participating in CoARA activities, aiming to exchange practices and learn from each other.	7.1. Regularly organized experience exchange visits/events , promoting continuous learning and collaboration among institutions implementing CoARA commitments, creating a more unified evaluation system.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
		7.2. Participate in national and international CoARA trainings .	7.2. Participation in national and international CoARA trainings.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

<p>8. Report / announce progress related to adherence to principles and implementation commitments.</p>	<p>This commitment will ensure that organizations provide each other with up-to-date information on the progress made. It will encourage thorough self-reflection and monitoring, adherence to principles, and progress in fulfilling commitments.</p>	<p>8.2. Publish information on progress achieved, publicizing results and implemented changes through both internal and external communication channels, involving the MAL scientific community as well as the entire community.</p>	<p>8.2. Publicly announced information about achieved results and future plans, thus promoting trust and adherence to commitments within the MAL community.</p>		X		X		X		X
--	--	---	--	--	---	--	---	--	---	--	---